

1 **Cytokine regulation in head and neck cancer.**

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6 We demonstrate through measurement of total transcription in the primary tumor by RNA-sequencing
7 silencing of the cytokine IL-18 in head and neck cancer. IL18 silencing was accompanied by activation of
8 *IL33*. Interleukin regulation in head and neck cancer *in vivo* occurred along with silencing of the chemokine
9 *Ccl21*.

10 Citations

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